

RESTAURANT MENU: LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL OVERVIEW

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The purpose of this article is to perform the analysis of the linguocultural characteristics of restaurant menus. Food culture is an essential component of the national mentality and an integral part of human life. Menu as a genre of gastronomic discourse has a set of characteristics relating to internal structure and pragmatic orientation. Cultural differences in the gastronomic norms and their expression in the menu texts give rise to complex problems in the process of intercultural communication and translation.

Keywords: *menu, translation process, linguistic peculiarities, structure, advertising, informative function, persuading function, intercultural communication*

MENIUL DE RESTAURANT: PREZENTARE LINGVISTICĂ ȘI CULTURALĂ

Prezentul articol are drept scop efectuarea unei analize a trăsăturilor lingvistice a meniului de restaurant. Cultura alimentară reprezintă o componentă esențială a mentalității naționale și o parte integrală a vieții. În calitate de tip de discurs gastronomic meniul posedă un set de caracteristici ce țin de structura sa internă și orientarea pragmatică. Diferențele culturale în normele gastronomice și expresia lor textuală în cadrul meniului contribuie la apariția unor probleme complexe în procesul de comunicare și traducere interculturală.

Cuvinte-cheie: *meniu, proces de traducere, particularități lingvistice, structură, publicitate, funcție informativă, funcție persuasivă, comunicare interculturală*

Any nation's history is closely connected with its gastronomic traditions (as a part of culture). Gastronomy reflects the life and customs of different nationalities being, along with language, one of the ways of culture study. Herewith, food denotations represent a notable object of language research. The XIXth century saw a surge of interest in nutrition as a cultural and linguistic phenomenon, when society began to view food as a unique cultural code. According to Jonathan Safran Foer (the author of the novel "Everything Is Illuminated"), "food is not rational, food is culture, habit, craving and identity" [1].

Renowned scholar Olyanich labelled the food phenomenon in linguistics as “*gluttonic*” (derived from the Latin term “*gluttonare*,” meaning “to consume and absorb food”). The author mentions that the linguistic markers of *gluttonic* discourse represent a single unity, which is further broken down into frames. These frames are then stored in the human mentality in the form of menus, recipes, table manners, norms, and customs. Olyanich asserts that food and its associated discourse form a sign system that embodies cultural capital, national and personal identity, subjective preferences, gender, and social class [2, p.169].

Gastronomic discourse represents a special type of social discourse, the purpose of which is to achieve optimal communication in the gastronomic sphere, where participants, conditions, methods of communications, the environment in which communication is carried out, the place and time of communication, goals and motives, as well as the genre and style of speech are taken into account. *Gluttonic* discourse reflects the essential aspects of the cultural, linguistic, religious, ethnic and ideological picture of the world. It acts as a basic element in national communication, since the concept of “cuisine” largely expresses the attitude and cultural perception of people. This type of discourse is represented by an extensive typology of *gluttonic* texts (recipes, menus, descriptions of gastronomic issues in fiction, etc.) [3].

The purpose of this article is to analyse a set of linguistic characteristics of a restaurant menu text and to study the peculiarities of bilingual (English/Romanian) *gluttonic* information display. The online menus of Andy’s Pizza restaurant available in the period April 10, 2023 – June 7, 2023 represent the source of the research corpus [4].

Restaurant menu is a significant part of the gastronomic culture and *gluttonic* discourse. According to the etymological sources, the word *menu* dates back to 1837 although the custom of making a list of the courses for a meal is much older. The word denote “a detailed list of dishes to be served at a banquet or meal,” derived from French *menu de repas* “list of what is served at a meal,” from French *menu* (adj.) “small, detailed” (11c.), from Latin *minutus* “small,” literally “made smaller” [5]. Initially, any concise inventory of details was referred to as a “menu”. However, during the appearance of restaurants in France in the early 19th century, the term gained new significance. Currently, a menu is a written compilation of dishes.

As stated by the specialized dictionaries, the word *menu* is bisemantic, referring to (1) list of dishes for each specific breakfast, lunch, dinner, changing daily and compiled for a day/ week/ month/ year, depending on the compiler's tastes and skills; (2) general list of dishes prepared in a restaurant or a café that remains unchanged in a certain eating place, being certainly different from the menus of other places [6].

Historically speaking, menus have been in existence for a long time and have undergone structural and content transformations over the years to adapt to the changing customs and traditions of society, from a simple list in which dishes are lined up to real “books” with leather-bound covers with inviting decorations and images. The earliest known menu dates back almost 3,000 years and was discovered on a stone tablet that was used to commemorate a grand celebration hosted by an Assyrian king named Ashurnasirpal II. The event was attended by approximately 70,000 people and lasted for over a week. Although the tablet contains descriptions of the food served, it cannot be considered a traditional menu, as it does not provide a list of dishes from which guests could order. The Chinese are believed to be among the first to use menus in a modern sense, with the appearance of restaurants during the Song Dynasty. The Middle Ages also saw the emergence of menus, with references made by poets such as Simone de Prodenzani and Bartolomeo Sacchi [7].

In terms of its printing and graphical design, the first present-day menu was created in 1855 in honor of Empress Eugénie at the court of Napoleon III. Artists, such as Gauguin, also contributed to the development of menus (Paul Gauguin “Menu Barbare”, Tahiti, 1900). In the USA, the “1834 Delmonico menu” is often cited as the first printed restaurant menu in the country [8]. The modern form of the menu, with a set order of courses and dishes, was invented by French chef Escoffier, referred to by the French press as *roi des cuisiniers et cuisinier des rois* (“king of chefs and chef of kings”) [9]. In earlier times, the menu was rather outsized and placed at the end of the table for everyone to read. Later, menus have become smaller/shorter and more numerous, with copies provided for each table. However, menus are much more than a mere inventory of food items. They serve as a reflection of cultural trends and social norms. Historical events, such as the Prohibition era and World War II, and even the counterculture movement of the 1960s have left their mark.

Menus have gradually undergone significant modifications, some of which may not be immediately noticeable. Modern menus employ subtle psychological tactics to influence customer behavior. For instance, the omission of the currency sign (£,\$,€,L) is deliberate and intended to make spending less daunting. Restaurants may strategically place an expensive item at the top of the page, making the other options appear more reasonably priced.

The menu represents the values of a restaurant and is perhaps the most important component of a restaurant's brand identity. By taking into account the latest culinary trends and carefully selecting the most appealing choices for food connoisseurs, a thoughtfully created menu has the potential to enhance the overall dining experience at the restaurant. A perfect menu must strike a delicate balance between educating customers about the ingredients, tastes, and cooking techniques of each dish while also highlighting the cultural distinctiveness of each one through its name, allowing it to transcend its mere physical appearance.

Linguistically, restaurant menus are hybrid texts that are informative and operative with an advertising function. As well as providing information about a dish's composition and preparation, their purpose is "to appeal to the expected addressee [...] to represent and advertise a restaurant" [10]. As a genre of gluttonic discourse, menus possess some characteristics of internal structure and pragmatic orientation. Herewith, one can distinguish two types of menus:

–A document in the field of public catering, where it stands for a collective compilation (chefs, cooks, economists). To emphasize the exclusivity of the food served in a particular restaurant (for promotional purposes), the menu is authored (e.g., menu à la chef). It also has a strict list of details: name of the restaurant, title of the document, list of dishes, their weight and price, date, signatures of authorized persons, seal.

–An advertising text, the purpose of which is to draw attention to the restaurant and to make a choice of one or another dish. Heston Marc Blumenthal, a British celebrity chef, and food writer, states, "If it doesn't taste good, it doesn't go on the menu" [1]. As an advertising text, the menu can keep all the above-mentioned elements, but it can be limited only by the list of dishes and their cost. The picture of the dish also has a marketing purpose (see Fig. 1).

Fig.1. Screenshot of Andy’s bakery [Accessed 3 May 2023].

Any menu is focused on the relationship between the addresser and the addressee. The addresser is a restaurant worker (chef, cook, waiter, server, etc.). The addressee is a person who reads the text of the menu (guests of the eating-place who are acquainted with the list of dishes served). In the advertising menu, potential consumers are often specified as the target audience, e.g., *fitness menu*, *kid’s menu*, *fasting menu*.

Participants	Time-Space Correlation	Function
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •addresser •addressee 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •visiting hours •eating place/take away 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •advertising •informative •persuading

Fig.2. Features of Menu

The length of a menu does not necessarily reflect its quality. When a menu is too short, customers may feel disappointed with the limited options. On the other hand, a long menu may have several ordinary dishes included. According to the opinion of Joseph Bastianich (American restaurateur and winemaker), “with four- appetizer and four entrée menus, it’s like, give me a break. That’s not a restaurant; that’s a dinner party” [1]. It is better to offer a smaller selection of high-quality dishes and prioritize meeting the customer’s needs, as they are the ones paying for the meal.

The manner in which the menu is presented to the customer has a significant impact. The layout of a menu has an influence on the visitor’s decision-making. It would be preferable if the design of the printed menu were to harmonize with the restaurant's or dining room's image, atmosphere, and decor. Upon perusing a menu from any given dining establishment, one cannot help but notice its meticulous arrangement - a sequential progression that cascades from tantalizing appetizers to savory soups and salads, culminating in the pièce de résistance of main entrées, then concluding with delectable desserts and quenching beverages.

Structurally, a menu (especially à la carte) is a carte containing sections and subsections. Each section is adorned with clear and distinct headings, boldly demarcated by boxes or borders, ensuring ease of navigation for the visitors. It is important to carefully consider the initial presentation of the meal, whether it is displayed on a wall outside the staff dining room, or handed over by the server to the guest. A presentation that is rushed or abrupt, whether it is written or spoken, can create a negative impression and diminish the expectation for the meal.

Fig. 3. Duality “length vs quality” in menus

Therefore, the communicative purpose of a restaurant menu is not just to inform the client about the set of dishes offered and their ingredients. Menus are designed to draw attention to the dishes, and convince customers to order them. It can be argued that the menu texts have signs of advertising messages in which they implemented strategies aimed at persuasion and attractiveness, as well as creating a positive emotional client mood.

The five types of menus most commonly used are: à la carte menus (which list the prices for each item separately), static menus (larger menu, typically divided into categories, not changing too often), du jour menus (daily change), cycle menus (with repeated options over a specific period of time), and fixed menus (menu with few options and a fixed total price) [11].

As the purpose of the menu is to convey information about the availability of dishes, their ingredients, and their method of cooking so that one can make a choice from the proposed variety, the names of the dishes (including their ingredients) represent an important component of the menu. The majority of dishes' names are phrases built on attributive and copulative models. At the lexical level, a menu's text is represented by the regionally marked vocabulary in the names of dishes. There is a geographical component functioning as an attributive component, its purpose being to emphasize the uniqueness of the dishes' origin, e.g., *pizza Neapolitana*, *Mexico soup*, *Greek salad*, etc. Another type of attributive relation is represented by a metaphorized component. Metaphors in cooking can help illustrate abstract concepts by drawing parallels

with tangible objects or processes with which the visitors are already familiar. Here, metaphorical linguistic expressions are defined as “words or other linguistic expressions that come from the language or terminology of the more concrete conceptual domain” [12, p. 4]. In this way, metaphors can create a mental image that provides a frame of reference for the culinary concept description. This is evident in the case of “*Pizza Diablo*,” which is cooked using such ingredients as salami, assorted sausages, mushrooms, olives, chili peppers, and mozzarella cheese. The combination of vibrant ingredients predominating in red and black as well as its pungent taste make reference to the Devil (the personification of evil as it is conceived in various cultures and religious traditions), the transference ground being color and pungency. Proper nouns may also function in attributive hypostasis. To illustrate the statement, *pizza Margherita*, *pizza Mario*, etc. will be mentioned. The famous *Caesar salad with chicken fillet* cooked from such savory, creamy, tangy, and crunchy ingredients as chopped romaine lettuce and garlicky croutons, tossed in a creamy dressing made with eggs, olive oil, lemon, and Parmesan, includes the name of its creator, restaurateur Caesar Cardini, an Italian immigrant who operated restaurants in Mexico and the United States [9]. A subtype of attributive relation in the framework of the dish’s name structure is represented by the denotation of the product as descriptive component(s): *beef salad*, *potato balls*, *spinach soup-purée*, *chicken soup*, *chicken skewers*, *lemon cheesecake*, etc. Moreover, the attributive relations are expressed by the use of adjectives reflecting the positive (delicious) nature of the dishes and expressing the attitude towards the dish, its properties, and taste, e.g., *chicken cream soup and mushrooms in crispy cake/supă cremă de pui și ciuperci în chiflă crocantă*.

Having a pronounced ethnocultural specificity, the names of dishes store in their semantics the traditions, customs, and experiences of peoples. The ingredients (*zeamă*, *solyanka*) or the proper names of their creators (*beef stroganoff*, *Olivier salad*, etc.) mainly implicitly or explicitly motivate the names of the dishes. The exploration of the dishes’ names helps to discover their national and cultural specifics. However, it is difficult to determine their internal form in cases of borrowed names. Etymological analysis of the corpus has determined a set of borrowings from English (*cheesecake*, *banana split*, *sandwich*, *steak*, *nuggets*, *BBQ*, *burger*), Italian (*bruschetta*, *ciabatta*, *focaccia*, *lasagna*, *calzone*), Russian (*solyanka*), French (*croissant*, *croquet*, *pané*), Tunisian (*shakshuka*),

Polish/Ukrainian (*draniki*), Spanish (*nachos*), Greek (*gyros*). The denotation of the mentioned dishes is maintained in the original language as they are generally accepted and commonly applied, easy to understand, and do not require translation due to the globalization of gastronomy. Such dishes can be found in any restaurant serving European cuisine.

The menu texts may also include quantitative data indicating, as a rule, the proportions, volume or quantity of ingredients, cooking time, or number of dishes or persons included in the meal: *pizza 5 cheeses /pizza 5 cașcavaluri*, *meat plate/ platou de carne*, *cheese plate/ platou de cașcavaluri*, *maxi plate with chicken wings/ platou maxi cu aripioare de pui*, *maxi plate with chicken nugget/ platou maxi cu nuggets de pui*. Here, the quantity is implicitly rendered by the semantic value of the noun *maxi* (denoting an extra-large amount of dish) and the noun *plate/platou*. According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, the word *plate* (polysemantic itself) is defined as (1) “a main course served on a plate” and (2) “food and service supplied to one person” [5]. The key word in the second definition is “one person.” However, the dish is placed in the category of “company”, so Romanian *platou* should be rendered into English as *platter* (“a large plate used especially for serving meat”). Consequently, the issue of the dish’s name translation comes into discussion.

Nowadays, different approaches are applied in the translation of dishes, especially if there is no total equivalent in the target language or a term already fixed in dictionaries. The menu’s structural and content features encode the choice of adequate translation, making it possible to identify a set of translation issues and show ways to solve them. Some dishes have a gastronomic or cultural equivalent recognized by both chefs and gourmards. This is certainly true in the case of the famous and much adored *Olivye/Olivier salad* (traditionally served on any holiday), known in European cultures as *Russian salad*, or *salată de boeuf* for Romanian gourmards. The history of this dish, of course, is not a revelation. Lucien Olivier created the salad in the 1860s for the Hermitage restaurant in Moscow.

Menus represent exceptional, infinite, sometimes witty, or even unintelligent examples of translation gaffes based on language and cultural interference. Inadequate translation of the dish’s name or its ingredients is the most frequently encountered challenge. A traditional Romanian dish called *brânzoaice* (*sweet cheese pastry*) is a cheese-filled pie made of leavened dough and is often translated as *crullers*. However, its English counterpart, *crullers*,

is defined as “a deep-fried pastry like a doughnut, often made from a rectangle of dough with a cut made in the middle that allows it to be pulled over and through itself, producing twists in the sides of the pastry” [9]. On analyzing the definitions, the content/ingredient divergences are evident: *brânzoaice* requires the presence of cheese in the dough, while the dough for *crullers* varies in European cuisine (no cheese). One of the most famous pasta recipes of Roman/Italian cuisine, *pasta/spaghetti Carbonara*, is translated into English as lowercase *carbonara paste* (as well as *paste polo and pastes with shrimps*). However, modern European gastronomy uses the term *pastă* (a dish of hot pasta into which other ingredients such as eggs, bacon or ham, and grated cheese have been mixed).

Therefore, as an integral part of the gastronomic discourse, regardless of its concise length, the menu contains a large amount of gluttonic information and reflects both the linguistic features of the text, and the national specifics of the food. The cuisine of certain ethnic groups reflects the spirit of culture and gastronomic preferences due to geographical and economic factors and traditions in which national spirituality and traces of historical background are attested. The translation of gastronomic (menu) texts requires knowledge and skills in the fields of cooking, linguocultural and sociocultural competence. The other side of the coin is that menu translation requires more creativity, since the task of the menu is not only to convey information but also to generate a favorable impression on the reader/visitor. The restaurant specifics also contribute to achieving the translation purpose, motivating the translation strategy applied.

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